

Customer satisfaction of Internet Banking users: A survey of customers in Pune

Vishal Wadajkar¹, Dr. Sonali Saha² and Adnan Arif³
¹Deputy Director - Academics, ²Associate Professor and ³Student,
Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

Objectives: This is a descriptive study to assess the customer satisfaction of internet banking users using a survey questionnaire.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive hypothesis was set and studied based on primary data collected from 125 internet banking users from Pune who were surveyed for customer satisfaction. The responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale for 10 sub-questions. The sample mean was compared against the hypothesized population mean of the scale mid-point of 2 and was tested for statistical significance at 95% confidence level.

Results: The study disclosed that the customer satisfaction of internet banking users was statistically significant. The mean was found to be well above the hypothesized population mean (Mean = 3.24; SD = 0.84).

Conclusion: The results of the study indicate that the customer satisfaction of internet banking users is well above a reasonable level.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, internet banking.

Introduction

As of 2017, India had 45 million active urban online banking users and it is expected to reach 150 million in 2020.

The technological advancement of the electronic channel of service delivery has gotten a level battleground for businesses by eliminating geographical, regulatory, and modern barriers. This revolution in the market place has set moving a revolution in the banking sector for the arrangement of a payment system that is compatible with the demands of the electronic marketplace. There are four electronic commerce activities internet users perform. These activities require a banking relationship and are: shopping, banking, investing, and online electronic payment for Internet services. The enormous increase of the internet is changing how businesses interact with consumers as most businesses are presently conducted utilizing the internet. It is this presentation of e-commerce as a means of payment that has urged banks to take a leap from the customary

banking services, offering a service unequivocally with the help of the internet, which has come to be known as internet banking or e-banking.

This new channel has added a new measurement to the idea of customer satisfaction and how it tends to be influenced positively. All businesses exist and endeavor to turn into an indispensable piece of the lives of their customers and hence consistently endeavor more diligently to continue satisfying their customers through better channels of conveying their contributions. Numerous components affect customer satisfaction, one of the most significant being service quality, which in turn has many attributes.

Given the growing penetration of internet marketing, we decided to survey internet banking users to assess their satisfaction levels.

The research question to be addressed is as follows:

RQ: Is there a reasonable level of customer satisfaction among internet banking users in Pune, India?

The term “reasonable” was operationalized at the mid-point of a 5-point Likert scale at the value of $(0+1+2+3+4)/5=2$, with 0 indicating can't say and 4 indicating completely satisfied.

Literature Review

The examination by Santouridis et al. (2009), researches internet service quality and its effect on customer satisfaction in the banking setting. Internet service quality is operationalized by a survey, and comprises of six measurements, to be specific assurance, quality of information, responsiveness, web assistance, empathy, and reliability. The field research, which brought about 184 substantial surveys, was directed among internet banking customers in Greece, a nation with a moderately low internet user rate. The discoveries affirm, generally, the legitimacy of the instrument and feature the better-than-expected execution of service quality conveyed by Greek banks through the internet.

A study by Ling et al. (2016) analyzed the variables which impact customer satisfaction towards Internet banking. The five elements which can impact customer satisfaction toward Internet banking incorporate service quality, web design and content, security and privacy, convenience, and speed. With the utilization of a poll review, 200 working adults who participated in this examination have given important input and reactions relating to the above components that impact customers' choice to do Internet Banking. The aftereffects of this exploration demonstrated that web design and content, convenience, and speed are firmly connected to customer satisfaction toward Internet banking.

The paper by Nimako et al. (2013), exactly looks at Customer Satisfaction (CS) with internet banking service quality (IBSQ) in the Ghanaian banking industry. The examination was a cross-sectional overview that utilized the utilization self-directed poll to gather essential information from an example of 200 respondents of two banks. It was discovered that, for the most part, customers of the two banks are dissatisfied with the promptness of reception of responses to customer requests, the capacity to be guided online to determine issues, also, the sensibility of the charges for internet banking transactions.

The study by Sakhaei et al. (2014), presents an examination to research service quality indexes in Internet Banking. The motivation behind this exploration is to understand the effect of service quality variables of Internet Banking on consumer loyalty in Iran. Six service quality measurements to be specific reliability, efficiency, responsiveness, fulfillment, security/privacy, and website design. The information was accumulated through a poll that was designed on a 5-Point Likert scale. The investigation shows that the Six service quality measurements have an important relationship with consumer loyalty in Internet Banking and reliability has the most connection and website design has the least connection to client fulfillment.

A contextual research gap clearly exists and hence this study was undertaken by surveying internet banking users in Pune.

Methodology

The research methodology adopted is outlined below:

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 125 (Bullen, 2016) internet banking users.
2. The selection of the 125 internet banking users was based on the judgment of the writer of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenient sampling was used.
3. The survey questionnaire had ten questions related to the various aspects of internet banking.
4. Responses were sought on 5-point Likert-scale.
5. For assessment of the customer satisfaction of internet banking users, the scale used was: 0- Can't say, 1- satisfied little, 2- satisfied somewhat, 3- satisfied well, 4- satisfied completely. The 10 sub-questions were: 1 - availability, 2 - speed, 3 – features, 4 – ease of use, 5 – privacy, 6 – security, 7 – customer service, 8 – responsiveness, 9- password and PIN reset, and 10 – simplified view.

Statement of Hypothesis:

Ho1: The level of customer satisfaction of the internet banking users is reasonable

Ha1: The level of customer satisfaction of the internet banking users is better than reasonable

Data analysis included descriptive analysis specifying features of the sample and the inferential analysis to test the hypothesis. A t-test was used given the fact that the SD of the population is not known, in which case, a Z-test could have been applied. The use of a t-test in practice is widely done as a substitute for the Z-test wherein the SD of the sample is taken as the SD of the population (given unknown population SD).

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88 that is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered as reliable.

Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis:

100 out of the 125 internet banking users were male while 25 were female. 39 users belonged to the age-group <30 years, 46 were from the age-group 30-40, while 40 were from the age-group >40 years. 43 users had internet banking experience in the range of <3 years, 41 in the range of 3-5 years, and 41 were having experience of more than 5 years. 73 respondents were from private banks while 52 were from public sector banks.

Inferential analysis:

The null hypothesis was set as the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). The alternate hypothesis was: $H_{a1}: \bar{x} > 2$. This was set based on the common knowledge that day-by-day internet banking is becoming more popular.

Summary of the ratings for customer satisfaction of internet banking users are given in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Summary of responses for customer satisfaction of internet banking users

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average satisfaction rating	3.34	3.26	3.16	3.21	3.34	3.18	3.17	3.22	3.34	3.21	3.24

Table 2 shows the testing of the hypothesis at 95% confidence level.

Table 2: Testing of the hypothesis

Parameter	H1 value
Sample Mean ($\bar{x}$)	3.24
Hypothesized population mean (μ)	2.00
SD of sample	0.84
n (sample size)	125
t-value= $\text{abs}((\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n}))$	16.58
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t,(n-1),1)$	0.00000
Decision	Reject Null

The null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternate that the sample mean is significantly different from the hypothesized population mean.

Discussion on results

The sample mean for the customer satisfaction of the internet banking users was 3.24 (SD = 0.84) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly higher than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2.

Conclusion

The research shows that customer satisfaction of the internet banking users is well above a reasonable level. Convenience and ease of use, have made internet banking a popular choice for banking transactions. With the rising levels on internet penetration the user base is also increasing.

As the study was based on sampling, limitations of sampling, in general, are applicable to it as well. Researchers are encouraged to study specific attributes of service quality which will add to the earlier research.

References

1. Bullen P B (2016). How to choose a sample size (for the statistically challenged). Accessed from <http://www.tools4dev.org/resources/how-to-choose-a-sample-size/>
2. Ling, G. M., Fern, Y. S., Boon, L. K., & Huat, T. S. (2016). Understanding customer satisfaction of internet banking: A case study in Malacca. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37(16), 80-85.
3. Nimako, S. G., Gyamfi, N. K., & Wandaogou, A. M. M. (2013). Customer satisfaction with internet banking service quality in the Ghanaian banking industry. *International journal of scientific & technology research*, 2(7), 165-175.
4. Sakhaei, F., Afshari, A., & Esmaili, E. (2014). The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in Internet banking. *Journal of mathematics and computer science*, 9(1), 33-40.
5. Santouridis, I., Trivellas, P., & Reklitis, P. (2009). Internet service quality and customer satisfaction: examining internet banking in Greece. *Total Quality Management*, 20(2), 223-239.